

Crossing the Cryptocurrency Chasm

Robert A. Wood^a

^a *Nexus University – Cryptocurrency Education and Certification, TX 75093, USA*

Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Cryptocurrency is the next big disruptive technology that will change human culture and create new trillion-dollar industries. Although it is bigger than the personal computer and the Internet technology waves combined, it still shares the same characteristics of all new emerging technologies as they strive to move from the initial technical domain adoption to the mainstream adoption of the general public.

2. Aim

To analyze and evaluate the necessary requirements to take cryptocurrency from the digital Internet to local hometown communities worldwide.

3. Material and methods

An exploration of historical technology disruptions will be introduced to better understand the maturation process and paths of adoption that are required by all new emerging technologies including cryptocurrency and its underlying distributed ledger technology.

4. Results

Several recent technologies were evaluated including personal computers, graphical user interfaces, and the Internet to discover the parallel conditions that effected and perpetuated their mainstream adoption.

5. Conclusions

According to the results of this analysis, every new emerging technology provided value to the marketplace beyond their technical features to provide new and better solutions that obsoleted the establishment by empowering the end-user and removing non-value adding middlemen.

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6. Keywords

Cryptocurrency; Mainstream Adoption; Marketplace value; Coin Utility

Author biography

Robert A. Wood Bob Wood was a senior technologist for over 25 years with both Ross Perot and Bill Gates companies and founded Shabang.com during the Internet gold rush, raising \$15M and building it to a \$200M corporation.

From 1998 to 2001, Mr. Wood served as the Chief Technology Officer and President & CEO for Shabang.com, an online e-commerce solution for merchants. Mr. Wood architected and built the first Internet product search engine that was the predecessor to Froogle, Amazon and eBay shopping.

From 1990 to 1995, Mr. Wood served as Senior Consultant and Developer with Microsoft Corporation. While at Microsoft he was responsible for assisting both the management and technical staffs of Fortune 500 corporations in understanding, architecting and constructing distributed application architectures.